

TigerMunch: An Application of GPT-4 Vision

Jeremiah Giordani, Isha Sinha, Aylin Hadzheiva

April 24, 2024

Abstract

TigerMunch is an innovative web application designed to analyze photos and textual descriptions of meals, subsequently providing nutritional estimates including calorie, fat, protein, and carbohydrate counts. This application integrates OpenAI's 'gpt-4-vision-preview' API to interpret images and the 'gpt-4-turbo-preview' API for processing textual descriptions. Through an advanced backend architecture, TigerMunch employs prompt chaining to sequentially process data from the vision model to the language model, enhancing the accuracy and reliability of nutritional assessments. This paper presents a comprehensive technical overview and evaluation of TigerMunch, demonstrating its capabilities and potential applications in dietary management and nutritional analysis.

Introduction

TigerMunch represents a significant advancement in the domain of dietary management, offering a user-friendly and efficient alternative to the traditionally laborious and error-prone methods of tracking nutritional intake. Conventional approaches often rely on manual data entry, which can be time-consuming and susceptible to inaccuracies. In contrast, TigerMunch automates this process by analyzing both images and textual descriptions of meals using cutting-edge artificial intelligence technologies. This automation not only simplifies the task but also enhances the consistency of nutritional tracking.

Despite the inherent challenges of achieving perfect accuracy in such estimations, TigerMunch aims to deliver results within the same margin of error as manual methods. This standard ensures that while the application prioritizes convenience, it does not compromise the reliability of its nutritional assessments. Achieving reasonable accuracy is pivotal, as nutritional data plays a crucial role in personal health management and dietary planning.

Central to the functionality of TigerMunch is the incorporation of GPT-4, the latest iteration of OpenAI's Generative Pre-trained Transformer models. GPT-4 is a state-of-the-art language model that possesses the ability to process both textual and visual inputs. When provided with images, GPT-4 can generate descriptive, textual outputs based on the contents of the images, a capability leveraged by TigerMunch to interpret meal photographs and produce nutritional data.

This paper will proceed by detailing the system's implementation and providing a comprehensive technical overview of the AI implementation of TigerMunch. Following this, we will discuss our method-

ological approach to evaluating the application using test data, and subsequently, we will present insights garnered from this evaluation, culminating in a thorough assessment of the system's performance and potential implications for users and the field of nutritional technology.

System Overview

TigerMunch is a comprehensive web application that seamlessly combines multiple technological components including frontend development, database management, charting capabilities, and integrations with advanced computer vision APIs. This section specifically delves into the core functionality provided by the AI API integration from OpenAI, which plays a pivotal role in processing images to generate nutritional estimates. While TigerMunch is capable of handling both images and textual descriptions of meals, our focus here will predominantly be on its image processing capabilities. We will explore how this integration not only supports but enhances the application's ability to provide accurate and timely nutritional data, essential for effective dietary management. This detailed overview aims to elucidate the technical intricacies and operational mechanics behind TigerMunch's innovative approach to meal analysis.

Backend Structure

When a user provides input on the page 'enter_meal_info.html', they can then press the "Submit" button. See Figure 1

When a user presses "Submit", the application calls the function on the route "/get_results". The method on the route "get_results" then takes the image input

Figure 1: Enter meal info page

and calls the method "handle_image" in the file "image_handler.py", passing in the image as a parameter and outputting a tuple of values in the form:

(Calories, Fat (g), Protein (g), Carbs (g))

The API interactions within TigerMunch are managed by the module named 'request_handler.py', which orchestrates the flow of image processing as follows. Figure 2 depicts the specified flow.

- The function 'describe_image' initiates the process by receiving an image, which it encodes into base64 format. This encoded image is then sent to the 'gpt-4-vision-preview' API. The API processes the image and returns a textual description of the meal depicted.
- Subsequently, the function 'get_estimates' utilizes the description provided by 'gpt-4-vision-preview'. It generates a JSON object containing nutritional estimates of calories, fats, proteins, and carbohydrates. The function then extracts these nutritional values from the JSON object and returns them as a tuple.

```
vision_module.py
1 import request_handler
2
3
4 def handle_image(image):
5     description = request_handler.describe_image(image)
6     values = request_handler.get_estimates(description)
7     # print(values)
8     return values
```

Figure 2: Backend Flow

This sequence ensures that the image data is efficiently converted into actionable nutritional informa-

tion, facilitating an automated and precise dietary analysis.

Describing Images

The function 'describe_image' takes in an image and outputs a string description of the meal. It begins by encoding the image in base 64. It then generates the 'payload' object, as described by the OpenAI API. The payload object essentially contains all of the information that the model needs to execute the task. This object contains the model for which the input should be run, 'gpt-4-vision-preview', the seed, which reduces randomness in output, the system message, which instructs the system what to do, and the base64 encoded image.

The system message is reproduced below:

- If you receive an image of a meal, please provide a detailed qualitative and quantitative description of the meal in the image, including identifiable food items, their approximate quantities, and any other observable details. Your description should be thorough enough to allow for an accurate analysis of the meal's nutritional content in a subsequent processing step, which will estimate the caloric content, the fat content, the protein content, and the carb content. If you receive an image of a Nutrition Label, instead of reporting all of that, you should report the number of servings per container, the number of calories, the grams of fat, the grams of carbs, and the grams of protein. Your response is limited to 200 tokens, so try to keep it as short as possible while providing all of the information.

The response message is then extracted and returned

Returning Estimates

Returning the estimates takes in, as a parameter, a description of the meal, and returns the estimates.

The output of GPT-4 is inherently unpredictable, requiring additional guardrails to ensure that the model outputs predictable results. The parameter "response_format" allows you to change the response type when calling the 'gpt-4-turbo-preview' API. Specifically, this value will default to text, outputting a textual description. However, for the purpose of returning estimates, where we aim to get the estimates in a meal based on a description, we set the 'response_format' to 'json_object'. This causes the API to return the output in JSON format. Once this object is returned, we can 'strip' the json, and then extract the four values we're looking for. We can then return these values as a tuple.

Thus, the function 'get_estimates' takes in a description and generates the 'payload' object, as described by the OpenAI API. This object contains the model for which the input should be run, 'gpt-4-turbo-preview', the seed, which reduces randomness is output, the response format, set to json_mode, the system message, which instructs the system what to do, and the description passed in as a parameter.

The system message is reproduced below:

- Given a detailed description of a meal, generate a JSON-formatted response estimating the meal's nutritional content. Please include the total calorie count, as well as the amounts of fat, protein, and carbohydrates, in grams. Structure your response with the following fields: 'calories' for the total calorie estimate, 'fat' for the fat content, 'protein' for the protein content, and 'carbs' for the carbohydrate content. Ensure your estimates are based on the provided meal description. You MUST provide only a single value for each field. You may NOT provide a range of values for any of the fields. Round to the nearest whole number

Prompt Chaining

It may not be clear why two models and two API calls are used here. The reason is that we've implemented a procedure in LLM prompt engineering known as prompt chaining [1]. Prompt chaining is a sophisticated technique employed in the TigerMunch application to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of processing inputs through different AI models sequentially. This method involves taking the output from one model and using it as the input for another, effectively chaining them together to utilize their strengths optimally.

In the context of TigerMunch, prompt chaining is implemented to capitalize on the specialized capabilities of two distinct models: the vision and language models. Initially, the 'gpt-4-vision-preview' API, which is fine-tuned for recognizing and describing objects within images, processes meal photos to generate textual descriptions. This model excels at visual interpretation due to its training on diverse datasets encompassing a wide range of objects and scenarios.

Following the vision model's output, the text description of the meal is then fed into a language model. Language models, particularly those like 'gpt-4-turbo-preview', are exceptionally adept at processing text to extract or calculate further details—in this case, nutritional information. This sequential use of models allows TigerMunch to leverage the vision model's accuracy in identifying meal components

from images and the language model's precision in interpreting textual data to estimate nutritional values.

The implementation of prompt chaining in TigerMunch therefore not only increases the overall accuracy of the application but also ensures that each model is used to its fullest potential: the vision model for accurate visual interpretations and the language model for detailed textual analyses. This approach maximizes the effectiveness of the AI components, leading to more reliable and comprehensive dietary assessments.

Evaluation Methodology

To ascertain the effectiveness of TigerMunch, we engaged in a structured evaluation using test data sourced from google images and research databases [2]. We then manually labeled the caloric and macronutrient information in a CSV file. This approach allowed us to measure the model's performance under controlled conditions.

Direct testing on the TigerMunch platform would have necessitated extensive manual data recording, which could introduce human error and bias. To circumvent these challenges, we opted to simulate the TigerMunch environment within a Python setup hosted on Google Colab. This simulation utilized the exact code base as TigerMunch, ensuring that any output generated in the Colab environment would be representative of what TigerMunch would produce in a live setting. See the attached artifacts for the 'ipynb' notebook file.

We carried out evaluations using three distinct test sets, each comprising a variety of images that reflect the range of meals users might upload to TigerMunch. For each test set, we processed the images using our simulated TigerMunch environment to determine the precision of the nutritional estimates. These estimates were then meticulously compared against the accurate nutritional values listed in the corresponding CSV files. The outcomes of our assessments are quantified by the average margin of error for calorie and macronutrient content, which we have recorded and depicted through graphs in the subsequent sections of this paper.

Test Set 1

Test Set 1 was composed of images featuring nutrition labels, which is a key scenario for the application of TigerMunch. An example from this test set is shown in Figure 3. Given that nutrition labels present information in a direct and clear format, it was anticipated that TigerMunch would yield high accuracy in these

cases.

Nutrition Facts	
Serving size 121 g/mL	
Servings Per Container --	
Amount Per Serving	
Calories 200	Calories from Fat 78
% Daily Value	
Total Fat 9g	13%
Saturated Fat 3g	13%
Cholesterol 20mg	7%
Sodium 358mg	15%
Total Carbohydrate 21g	7%
Dietary Fiber 1g	4%
Sugars 8g	
Protein 8g	
Vitamin A 10%	Vitamin C 7%
Calcium 9%	Iron 6%

Figure 3: Test Set 1 Example Image

The performance of TigerMunch on Test Set 1 was highly satisfactory, with the system reliably extracting caloric and macronutrient data from the nutrition labels. The precision of TigerMunch’s readings is illustrated in Figure 4, where the accuracy averaged over three trials for all images in this dataset is presented. Accuracy was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Accuracy} = 1 - \left| \frac{\text{estimated value} - \text{ground truth}}{\text{ground truth}} \right|$$

In these evaluations, TigerMunch demonstrated an exceptional ability to accurately recognize and relay nutritional information, with a consistent performance across the board.

Test Set 2

Test Set 2 comprised images of typical food items, as exemplified in Figures 5 and 6. This test set was crucial in evaluating TigerMunch’s core capability: the accurate recognition and estimation of macronutrient content in meal images. The images for this test were sourced from Google Images, with nutritional

Figure 4: Test Set 1 Performance

information obtained from authoritative sources associated with each food item.

Figure 5: Test Set 2 Example Image

Figure 6: Test Set 2 Example Image

TigerMunch exhibited a strong performance with Test Set 2. While no direct comparison with human estimation was undertaken, the proficiency of TigerMunch in analyzing the images from this set was notable. Figure 7 demonstrates TigerMunch’s effectiveness, highlighting a 76% accuracy rate in caloric estimation. As for the macronutrients, the accuracies stood at 74% for fats, 57% for proteins, and 80% for carbohydrates. These figures reflect TigerMunch’s reliable functionality in processing everyday meal images to extract nutritional data.

Figure 7: Test Set 2 Performance

Test Set 3

The evaluation involving Test Set 3 was pivotal, standing as the most crucial among our trials. This set included images used in an academic study that gauged human proficiency in estimating the carbohydrate content from an array of food items [2]. The 2018 study encompassed a broad spectrum of foods—ranging from dairy, fruits, and vegetables, to grains, meats, and complete dishes such as hamburgers and sandwiches—and drew upon the judgments of 2028 participants. Figure 8 display representative samples from this collection.

Figure 8: Test Set 3 Images

The significance of Test Set 3 stems from our foundational aim for TigerMunch to match or surpass human-level accuracy in nutritional estimation. Recognizing the inherent limitations of AI, and the greater ease and user-friendliness of TigerMunch compared to conventional tracking methods, it was essential to verify that the system could at least equate human performance in this respect.

To this end, we assessed TigerMunch’s efficacy on the same dataset previously evaluated by the human subjects, focusing solely on calorie estimation—macronutrients were not part of this analysis. Beyond gauging absolute accuracy percentages, we

examined the system’s accuracy based on the proportion of images for which it could estimate caloric content within a 20% margin of the true value. The findings of this examination are presented in Figures 9 and 10.

Figure 9: Test Set 3 Performance

The findings from Test Set 3 reveal a noteworthy performance disparity between TigerMunch and human evaluators in identifying caloric content from images. With a mean absolute accuracy rate of approximately 73%, TigerMunch substantially outperformed the human participants, who achieved an average accuracy rate of only 42%. Furthermore, TigerMunch accurately classified more than half of the images—an average of 11.5 out of 20—within a 20% margin of the actual caloric values, a considerable improvement over the human average of just 5.15 out of 20. This tells us that TigerMunch performs significantly better than human estimators ($P < 0.0001$)

These results are indicative of TigerMunch’s advanced capability to process visual information and extract nutritional data with a high degree of precision. The practical implications of such a perfor-

Figure 10: Test Set 3 Performance

mance are significant. This level of accuracy ensures that TigerMunch can serve as a reliable tool for individuals seeking to manage their diets more effectively, providing them with a convenient and accurate means to assess their nutritional intake. In a broader context, these results underscore the potential of AI to enhance and perhaps even transform nutritional tracking, empowering users with instant and precise information that was previously accessible only through labor-intensive methods or professional consultation. While its performance is not perfect, the ability to yield results more accurate than human estimates is significant.

Prompt Chaining

Besides assessing accuracy, we also explored the performance enhancements brought by the implementation of prompt chaining. To quantify its impact, we reconfigured the backend to simulate TigerMunch's operation without the use of prompt chaining and then conducted tests on Test Set 3. The outcomes of this comparative analysis are depicted in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Test Set 3 Performance, With and Without Prompt Chaining

The contrast in results is telling. The integration of prompt chaining resulted in an increase in accuracy—from 68.5% without prompt chaining to 73.6% with it. While this improvement is not very large, it is significant. Prompt chaining optimizes the AI's data processing capabilities by systematically breaking down the task into stages, allowing each stage to focus on what it does best—visual recognition followed by textual analysis in this case. By using the strengths of each AI model sequentially, prompt chaining can reduce compounding errors that might arise from a single model attempting to process complex information outside its optimized capacity.

Conclusion

The central contributions of this paper can be summarized as follows:

1. The development and validation of TigerMunch, an innovative web application utilizing the latest advancements in AI for nutritional analysis.

2. A comprehensive evaluation of TigerMunch's accuracy in estimating nutritional content, demonstrating superior performance compared to traditional human estimations ($P < 0.0001$)
3. The empirical analysis of the impact of prompt chaining on the accuracy of nutritional estimates, illustrating its significance in enhancing AI performance.

The implications of these findings are multifaceted. Primarily, they validate the effectiveness of employing sophisticated AI models in the realm of nutritional tracking, showcasing the potential to exceed human capabilities in terms of accuracy and reliability. Furthermore, the demonstrable benefits of prompt chaining affirm its role as a critical technique in the development of complex AI systems, suggesting that its use could be extended to other applications requiring nuanced data interpretation. The success of TigerMunch paves the way for future innovations in dietary management tools, potentially revolutionizing how individuals track and understand their nutritional intake. This work also sets a precedent for further explorations into the integration of diverse AI functionalities to tackle intricate problems across various domains.

References

- [1] Tongshuang Wu et al. "PromptChainer: Chaining Large Language Model Prompts through Visual Programming". In: *Extended Abstracts of the 2022 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. CHI EA '22. New Orleans, LA, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2022. ISBN: 9781450391566. DOI: 10.1145/3491101.3519729. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3491101.3519729>.
- [2] Jun Zhou et al. "Calorie Estimation From Pictures of Food: Crowdsourcing Study". In: *Interact J Med Res* 7.2 (Nov. 2018), e17. ISSN: 1929-073X. DOI: 10.2196/ijmr.9359. URL: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/30401671>.
- [3] OpenAI et al. *GPT-4 Technical Report*. 2024. arXiv: 2303.08774 [cs.CL].
- [4] Tongshuang Wu et al. "PromptChainer: Chaining Large Language Model Prompts through Visual Programming". In: *Extended Abstracts of the 2022 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. CHI EA '22. New Orleans, LA, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2022. ISBN: 9781450391566. DOI: 10.1145/3491101.3519729. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3491101.3519729>.
- [5] Jason Wei et al. "Chain-of-Thought Prompting Elicits Reasoning in Large Language Models". In: *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*. Ed. by S. Koyejo et al. Vol. 35. Curran Associates, Inc., 2022, pp. 24824–24837. URL: https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper_files/paper/2022/file/9d5609613524ecf4f15af0f7b31abca4-Paper-Conference.pdf.
- [6] Hamid Hassannejad et al. "Automatic diet monitoring: a review of computer vision and wearable sensor-based methods". In: *International Journal of Food Sciences and Nutrition* 68.6 (2017). PMID: 28139173, pp. 656–670. DOI: 10.1080/09637486.2017.1283683. eprint: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09637486.2017.1283683>. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09637486.2017.1283683>.
- [7] Manisha Singla and Vinay Kumar. "IoT Based Computer Vision System for Nutrition Management". In: (June 2019). working paper or preprint. DOI: 10.1109/ISPC48220.2019.8988487. URL: <https://hal.science/hal-02156884>.
- [8] David Herzig et al. "Volumetric Food Quantification Using Computer Vision on a Depth-Sensing Smartphone: Preclinical Study". In: *JMIR Mhealth Uhealth* 8.3 (Mar. 2020), e15294. ISSN: 2291-5222. DOI: 10.2196/15294. URL: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/32209531>.
- [9] Kaylen J. Pfisterer et al. "Towards Computer Vision Powered Color-Nutrient Assessment of Pureed Food". In: *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR) Workshops*. June 2019.
- [10] Marios Anthimopoulos et al. "Computer Vision-Based Carbohydrate Estimation for Type 1 Patients With Diabetes Using Smartphones". In: *Journal of Diabetes Science and Technology* 9.3 (2015). PMID: 25883163, pp. 507–515. DOI: 10.1177/1932296815580159. eprint: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1932296815580159>. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1932296815580159>.
- [11] Wenjing Shao et al. "Vision-based food nutrition estimation via RGB-D fusion network". In: *Food Chemistry* 424 (2023), p. 136309. ISSN: 0308-8146. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2023.136309>. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0308814623009275>.